

Chemical Investigations on *Picris hieracioides* Linn and *Phayloopsis Parviflora* Willd

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Chemical investigations on the leaves of *Picris hieracioides* Linn^{1,2,3} and *Phayloopsis parviflora* Willd¹ resulted in the isolation of three sterols of which two have been characterised as β - and γ -sitosterol.

P*CICRIS HIERACIOIDES* Linn (Compositae), the only available plant of this genus in India is an erect coarse herb, distributed over the temperate Himalayas and Nilgiris. *Phayloopsis parviflora* Willd (Acanthaceae) is a prostrate closely branched herb distributed throughout India (except the N.W.), alt. 0-3000 ft, and is common in Bengal.

Dried and powdered leaves of both the plants were extracted successively with pet. ether (60°-80°), benzene and chloroform. The petrol and benzene extracts were then further separated into neutral and acidic fractions, by shaking with 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution.

The neutral and acidic fractions were chromatographed over columns of neutral alumina and silica gel G respectively. The chloroform extract of the plant materials were chromatographed over silica gel G directly after removal of the solvent.

The neutral fractions of the pet. ether (60°-80°) and benzene extracts of *P. hieracioides* yielded the same crystalline material which was purified through repeated chromatographies over columns of neutral alumina and silica gel G and was characterised by its m.p. 135°-136°, and $[\alpha]_D - 34.8^\circ$ (CHCl₃), acetate m.p. 129°-130° [literature⁶; β -sitosterol, m.p. 136°-137°; $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$ (CHCl₃); β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 134°] as β -sitosterol. This was further confirmed by its m.m.p. and by its agreement on T.L.C. with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol.

The chloroform extract of the same plant gave on chromatography over silica gel G another sterol (Liebermann-Burchard test positive) in small quantities, which was obtained pure as its acetate. The sterol acetate which gave a single spot on T.L.C. had m.p. 160°, and its R_f values in the solvent systems of EtOH : EtOAc (1 : 3) and C₆H₆ : EtOAc (3 : 1) over plates of silica gel G were found to be 0.80 and 0.57 respectively. The compound gave a faint yellow

colouration with tetranitromethane. Further study and characterisation of the compound is in progress.

The neutral fraction of the pet. ether (60°-80°), extract of *P. parviflora* afforded two crystalline compounds having close R_f values, which were finally separated by chromatography over silica gel G. On elution with pet. ether (60°-80°) : C₆H₆ (2 : 1) a low melting solid, m.p. 74°-75° was obtained, and elution with pet. ether (60°-80°) : C₆H₆ (1 : 1) solvent system followed by repeated crystallisations from CHCl₃-MeOH, gave γ -sitosterol, m.p. 146°-147°, $[\alpha]_D - 43.64^\circ$ (CHCl₃), acetate, m.p. 138°-139.5° [literature⁶, γ -sitosterol, m.p. 147°-148°, $[\alpha]_D - 43.13^\circ$ (CHCl₃), m.p. of γ -sitosterol acetate, 143°]. Its identity with γ -sitosterol was finally confirmed by its m.m.p. and single spot on mixed T.L.C. with an authentic sample of γ -sitosterol.

Neither of the plants gave any tests for alkaloids, with Mayer's and Dragendorff's reagents.

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